

Dataset belonging to: Local interactions lead to spatially correlated gene expression levels in bacterial groups.

By: Simon van Vliet*, Alma Dal Co, Annina R. Winkler, Stefanie Spriewald, Bärbel Stecher, & Martin Ackermann

* Institute of Biogeochemistry and Pollutant Dynamics, Department of Environmental Systems Science, ETH Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland
& Department of Environmental Microbiology, Eawag, Dübendorf, Switzerland
simon.vanvliet@eawag.ch

This dataset contains all RAW-data belonging the manuscript “Local interactions lead to spatially correlated gene expression levels in bacterial groups”. A second dataset containing processed data has been uploaded to datadryad.org (see reference in manuscript).

The data set contains a zip file for each genetic pathway. Each replicate experiment is located in the folder: **/[gene name]/[yyyy-mm-dd]/[colony name]/**, where colony name is typically yymmdd-[unique identifier].

This folder contains subfolders

- **images:** contains raw image data. File names follow Schnitzcells conventions, i.e. [colony name]-[c]-[nnn].tif, where [c] specifies color channel (p=phase, g=GFP, r=RFP) and [nnn] indicates frame number, starting from 001.
- **data:** contains Schnitzcells lineage tracking data [colony name]_lin.mat and [colony name]_Tdata.mat and extracted fluorescent data: cellDataTimeArray.mat (created with ExtractFluorescenceData)
- **segmentation:** contains Schnitzcell segmentation data. Each frame has its own data file with name [colony name]seg[nnn].mat.
- **cellSegmentationData:** contains extracted geometric properties for cell, created with createCellOutlinesSmallFile. Each frame has its own data file with name [colony name]_segData[nnn].mat.